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Existential silos: The compartmentalization of the futures of environmental change and the nuclear threat[☆]

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ABSTRACT

Nuclear weapons and environmental change are two existential threats to humanity. This article shows that current policy and academic discourse neglects their possible future interactions and proposes a research agenda to undo this compartmentalization. Based on a comprehensive review of policy documents and scholarship on nuclear and environmental security futures between 1990 and 2024, this article documents the compartmentalization of these threats. It shows that prevalent security imaginaries do not account for interactions and instead treat environmental change and nuclear weapons as different types of security threat. This creates a number of epistemic and material vulnerabilities which must be addressed by scholarship. The article lays out avenues to map out material and political interactions between the two threats. It urges policymakers and scholars to integrate imaginations of the implications of these and other existential threats for the future of humanity.

Today, 12,000 nuclear weapons still threaten the Earth, with nuclear-armed states planning to extend their arsenals' lifespan at least until 2090.¹ At the same time, the Earth system is transforming rapidly. Even optimistic forecasts suggest warming would not stop until long after reaching net zero, which under current commitments would happen in 2060 at the earliest ([Climate Action Tracker, 2024](#)). More broadly, "environmental change", by which we mean the wider ongoing process of anthropogenic changes in the Earth System, threatens humanity's "safe operating space" as determined by nine planetary boundaries, of which six have already been crossed ([Richardson et al., 2023](#); [Steffen et al., 2015](#), p. 737). By the end of the century, environmental change will likely result in major alterations of the Earth with significant implications for the security landscape, if current climate policies continue ([Lenton et al., 2023](#)). How exactly this world looks depends on mitigation efforts, but also on unpredictable tipping points and systemic risks ([Kemp et al., 2022](#)). Our preparedness for these uncertain conditions depends on our imagined futures: sets of assumptions about what possible future worlds could consist of, which (re)produce the boundaries of conceivable or desirable actions in the present as well as the order of priorities ([Beckert, 2016](#); [Pelopidas, 2016](#)). In light of the unpredictability and gravity of environmental change, it is

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¹ 2090 is the expected lifespan of the next generation of French SSBNs and the furthest explicitly made projection into the future ([Parly, 2021](#)).

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particularly important to understand how these processes could intersect with risks of nuclear weapons use and nuclear war.

This is because nuclear weapons technology is currently unique in that its speed and scale of destructivity preclude any effective mitigation (Maurer, 2016). The US posture, for instance, enables 90 million casualties over less than three hours (Montoya & Kemp, 2023). This scenario has so far been avoided not just because of statesmen's decisions, but thanks to fortuitous disobedience and technological failures (Pelopidas, 2017; Schlosser, 2013; Sherwin, 2020). AI-driven automation of command and control promises to "deprive humanity even of that luck" (Zala, 2024, p. 157). Given the inevitability of a significantly climate-changed future, the particularly unmitigable nature of nuclear war, and the diverse crisscrossing pathways to disaster, it is crucial to consider how these two existential threats might develop and interact. This is not enough to completely understand humanity's future; a wide array of existential threats looms over our societies. A better understanding of how not only nuclear weapons and environmental change, but artificial intelligence, pandemics, or biotechnologies may all affect each other is needed. In writing this paper, we hope to contribute to existing thinking on systemic risks and to catalyze similar research on other sets of threats.

This article investigates the imagined futures of security relating to environmental change and nuclear weapons that are currently being articulated by policymakers and scholars. It identifies a pattern of compartmentalization whereby the two threats are not treated as interactive but as different types of security threat.

Methodologically, this paper identifies those imagined futures through a review of policy documents and the literature published in environmental policy and nuclear security studies between 1990 and 2024. We conduct a quantitative literature review using the Scopus database to identify and characterize scholarly work on nuclear weapons policy and climate policy. We combine this with an analysis of major climate and security strategies as well as military climate adaption and nuclear policy debates in China, France, Russia, the United Kingdom, and the United States to trace imagined futures for security among policymakers.²

We aim to make two contributions. Firstly, we make an empirical contribution by comprehensively documenting the phenomenon of compartmentalization in both policy planning and academic thinking for the first time. Second, we map possible connections between two major existential threats and contribute to a better understanding of these across security studies and existential risk studies. No systematic framework for such interactions currently exists.³ Nuclear weapons dynamics have been studied mostly within the field of International Relations, which is marked by "survivability bias", a blindness to the possibility of extinction or state-system collapse (Pelopidas, 2020, p. 465), and a difficulty in thinking beyond its established state-centric models of security (McDonald, 2024; Sears, 2021).

This article is organized into four parts. The first analyzes the selected policy documents, finding that the imagined futures articulated within them disconnect environmental change from nuclear⁴ policy dynamics. The second section shows a similar divergence in existing scholarship. A third section lays out how existing connections in nuclear energy policy, global governance and nuclear winter can be deepened to reflect a more interactive conceptualization. Finally, the last section lays out which other material and political connections are likely to exist and suggests avenues for research connecting nuclear and climate futures.

1. Compartmentalization in policymaking

The first place we expect imagined futures of environmental and nuclear threats to be articulated is in states' preparation for them. All states should anticipate being affected by both threats. However, only nuclear-armed states can independently determine future nuclear risks. This section therefore studies how the threats are conceptualized by nuclear-armed states, though we are cognizant that alternative futures may be articulated by other actors. We examine the national security and climate adaptation policies of China,⁵ France, Russia, the United Kingdom, and the United States.⁶ As the five permanent members of the United Nations Security Council and the Nuclear Weapons States under the Non-Proliferation Treaty, they have a particular responsibility for global security and the nuclear order. They also significantly contribute to both nuclear and environmental risks, holding over 96 % of the world nuclear arsenal in 2024 (Kristensen et al., 2025) while accounting for around 48 % of global greenhouse gas emissions in 2023 (European Commission, 2024).

All five states increasingly integrate both environmental concerns and nuclear weapons into strategic policy. National security strategies and military doctrines in France, the UK, and the US in particular have treated climate issues as a central part of their imagined strategic environments since the mid-2000s. Their impacts are treated in a different frame than those shaping nuclear weapons. Environmental change is considered mostly as a direct but not existential threat to human communities and resources. Using Vogler's categorization of environmental threats in National Security Strategies between 2000 and 2022, we find that of 188 references to specific environmental threats, 62.8 % related to "first-order effects" like natural disasters, resource scarcity, or food shortages in the five nuclear states' security strategies (Vogler, 2023, p. 5). Second-order effects mostly concerned resource-driven conflicts, often in the Global South, making up a further 10.6 % of mentions. Unmanageable alterations to the conditions of 'great power' relations were

² See the Annex for a list of documents studied.

³ A recent effort in that direction is (Egeland, 2025)

⁴ Unless otherwise specified, we use the word "nuclear" to refer specifically to nuclear weapons-related issues, rather than broader nuclear phenomena.

⁵ We would like to thank our colleague Nicola Leveringhaus for her invaluable help in examining the Chinese case.

⁶ The four other nuclear-armed states (India, Israel, North Korea, and Pakistan) are not included due to insufficient information access. All four are highly secretive and publish neither nuclear strategies nor force sizing plans. Given the lack of transparency around NATO and Russian nuclear weapons deployment on other territories, we also do not analyze the policies of hosting states.

not envisioned. By contrast, nuclear weapons futures are defined by threats from adversarial states, changes in deterrence relationships brought on by new technologies, and nuclear proliferation to new states. This reflects the goal of nuclear strategy – to manage risks of major inter-state war through deterrence. That *desired* effect of nuclear strategy operates at a different level from imagined environmental futures, and is articulated separately from environmental security policy. Russia in particular discounts climate-military connections: while its *National Security Strategies* reference environmental threats, no *Military Doctrine* does. But across all states' documents, the two threats never substantively appear in the same paragraph except as list items and, in one British document, to note links between climate change mitigation, nuclear energy, and weapons proliferation (Cabinet Office, 2008, p. 23).

The envisioned environmental risks would seem to extend to climate impacts on nuclear bases. Yet major national climate adaptation strategies do not mention nuclear weapons-related risks. This is perhaps unsurprising given their breadth. However, in the 2020 s, the US, UK, and France have also produced military-specific climate strategies. None of these mention nuclear weapons, either. The burgeoning concern for military adaptation at times even disappears when applied to nuclear issues. The US *National Defense Strategy* references problems in bases' resilience to environmental change, including at those "vital for deterrence objectives" (U.S. Department of Defense, 2022, p. 20), whereas the *Nuclear Posture Review* makes no mention of them. The separation between environmental concerns and nuclear strategy again suggests that states do not consider the implications of environmental change as meaningful to nuclear thinking.

Naturally, climate adaptation of military installations generally will include those where nuclear weapons are present. But it remains unclear how such installations' climate vulnerabilities are assessed, if specific nuclear vulnerabilities are considered, and if these beget meaningful adaptation. Vulnerability assessments are not publicly available for France, Russia, and China. France only recently identified the need for climate adaptation and has not formulated an approach. Since the 2011 Fukushima disaster, it has worked on securing specifically nuclear-related sections of naval installations from rising sea levels and extreme weather, but costs and assessment methods are unknown (Cour des comptes, 2024, pp. 455–456).

The US and UK do publish risk assessments for nuclear weapons installations. The UK Ministry of Defence models change until 2050, whereas the modernized nuclear arsenal is supposed to serve into the 2060 s. Moreover, published documentation regarding Clyde Naval Base – which hosts the British nuclear submarine force – notes broad regional climate trends, but without drawing conclusions about their future impact on the base itself. (Defence Infrastructure Organisation, 2017). In the US, Department of Defense evaluations of nuclear bases have not so far been made public. No references to nuclear weapons appear in its reports on installation vulnerability, and it is questionable how methods account for nuclear-specific vulnerabilities (Pinson et al., 2021). The National Nuclear Security Administration's (2023) Stockpile Stewardship Program did, for the first time, refer to the need to "address climate adaptability and resilience", but provided no details on what this entailed (, (p. 5.19). The Department of Energy's assessment of Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory found most of its assets highly vulnerable to heat waves, increased precipitation, reduced precipitation, wildfires, and reduced water supply (Fratanduono et al., 2022, pp. 10–11). It is unclear if this affected budget requests, meaning that climate assessments do not seem to trigger serious adaptation efforts. Outside studies suggest that both British and US nuclear base adaptation rely on overly conservative vulnerability assessments (Dorfman, 2021; Kwong, 2023). As a result of these factors, as well as their limited ambition in mitigating specific risks to existing infrastructure, climate adaptation policy does not formulate serious implications for nuclear arsenals. This mirrors the disconnect between deterrence-strategic and climate-security thinking.

That disconnect should be overcome when formulating long-term policy decisions. We therefore examined the legislative debates around the ongoing "modernization" of nuclear arsenals in France, the UK, and the US.⁷ Systems currently under development should be adapted for a climate-changed future, as they are to be deployed at least until the 2060 s, for the UK's *Dreadnought* class submarine (Mills, 2023), and even up to 2120, for US plutonium pits (Rodgers & Hersman, 2021, p. 3).

Yet the records of debates and reports from both British Houses of Parliament, the US House and Senate Armed Forces Committees, and the Defense Committees of both French houses of parliament⁸ make almost no reference to environmental change as a relevant issue to nuclear weapons policy. The records we examined were those relating to legislation on nuclear modernization – the 2006 *White Paper on the Future of the United Kingdom's Nuclear Deterrent* and subsequent debates on the Nuclear Deterrent in the UK, *National Defense Authorization Acts* starting from the Obama administration in the US, and the 2018 and 2023 *Lois de Programmation Militaire* for France. In almost none of these debates do witnesses, evidentiary reports, or representatives raise environmental change. This suggests that the compartmentalization observed in strategic documents does not reflect an informed conclusion that there is no need to connect them. Rather, the question of potential mutual relevance seems not to be asked in the first place.

The British debate is instructive as it contains the few identified climate considerations, though without generating serious reflection. In the evidence submitted to the Select Committee on Defence, several witnesses raised the opportunity costs of nuclear modernization and the inability of nuclear deterrence to address environmental threats (House of Commons Defence Committee, 2006a, 2006b, 2007). Yet the Government's response ignored environmental change. In later debate, a lone member of the House of Lords questioned the wisdom of investing in a nuclear deterrent when environmental change posed a larger threat and was dismissed (Armed Forces, 2007, Column 1146–1147). This same dynamic played out in a subsequent vote in 2013–2014; evidence on environmental connections was offered by witnesses, almost none made it into reports, and no discussion followed. Nuclear policy was thus

⁷ Records of Russian and Chinese nuclear policymaking processes are not sufficiently available to ascertain the role of environmental considerations.

⁸ Retrieved from <https://hansard.parliament.uk/>, <https://www.govinfo.gov/app/collection/chrq/118>, <https://www.assemblee-nationale.fr/dyn/16/comptes-rendus/seance>, and https://www.senat.fr/compte-rendu-commissions/affaires-etrangeres_archives.html, respectively.

formulated without consideration of environmental change even when an opportunity to address it was presented. French nuclear discourse has gone out of its way to delegitimize environmental concerns as relevant to nuclear policy. In 2023, a proposed constitutional law supported by 89 MPs claimed that the “environmentalist ideology” and “militant ecologist associations from the left” threatened the country’s arsenal (Proposition de Loi Constitutionnelle, 2023, pp. 4–5). The fact that compartmentalization occurs not only in policy documents, but in further debates strongly suggests that the underlying conceptualization of them as separate issues is widely shared.

The imagined futures expressed in three types of policymaking reflect a failure to connect nuclear weapons to environmental change. At the most general level, national security strategies treat the two as separate domains affecting different types of security. In climate adaptation policy, assessment of nuclear bases’ vulnerability proceeds on a limited scale and specificity. It is possible that other specific connections are made in unknown, non-publicly-accessible workstreams. Much nuclear policy work happens behind closed doors, which restricts our analysis. That being said, it seems doubtful that such work meaningfully undoes the compartmentalization reproduced in both policy documents and public debates. Political struggles over state resources and public legitimacy will continue to be informed by the dominant framings presented in the examined doctrines and policy documents. If an alternative security imaginary exists but is shared only among a small and specialized group of actors, its influence over the formulation of public policy as a whole is limited (Pelopidas, Taha, & Vaughan, 2024).

2. Compartmentalization in the academic literature

A survey of the academic literature shows a similar compartmentalization. Using the Scopus database,⁹ we conducted a quantitative review of the literatures on nuclear weapons and climate security. Keyword searches related to nuclear¹⁰ and climate¹¹ threats in abstracts, titles, and keywords of peer-reviewed articles, books, and book chapters published in English between 1990 and 2024 were conducted in May 2025.

This identified 439 studies which cover both threats in various disciplines.¹² That literature is small, though it is growing in absolute terms (Fig. 1).¹³ It accounts for 1.6 % of publications dedicated to nuclear security¹⁴ and an infinitesimal proportion of total work on climate change. Moreover, much of this work still fails to cross the divide of compartmentalization. The threats often appear as analogous cases or parallel developments rather than as interactive ones. Most works do not identify mechanisms for interaction. Just 72 do so clearly, of which 56 relate to the position of nuclear energy as both a proliferation risk and a potential decarbonization strategy. A further 61 identify partial links, laying out factors like ideology or emergency preparedness which shape both threats but do not translate into clear interactive effects. 65 discuss the climatic consequences of nuclear war or historical legacies of nuclear testing and weapons production, without relating these to the broader threat of anthropogenic environmental change.

The overwhelming majority of results treat the two as parallel (i.e. shaping a third process but without mutual interaction) or analogous (sharing certain features or constituting subsets of a broader category). In the first case, they are often items in the same policy agendas or elements taken up by the same artistic, activist, and philosophical movements. In the second, they are used as static analogies of one another. Most commonly, both are treated as threats of a unique scale, transcending national sovereignty and menacing all life. Their shared characterization as “collective action problems” or as issues which transcend sovereignty leads to comparative analyses of their dynamics. This frame can be used to identify important commonalities and problematize structures that make them possible. It can also translate ethical concepts, such as intergenerational (in)justice (Palombella, 2023; Rendall, 2007), or political constructions, like “Fossil-fuel free-zones” (Green, 2022) or a “Fossil-fuel non-proliferation treaty” (Newell et al., 2022). However, analogous and parallel discussions necessarily sustain the compartmentalization of both threats. They are comparable, not interactive. At their most problematic, they can invisibilise or historicize the nuclear threat. Drawing direct inspiration from the history of nuclear governance ascribes a debatable level of success to the nuclear security architecture which portrays nuclear weapons as a past and managed threat even as we enter a new arms race.

Given that the existing literature barely addresses interactions, it is perhaps unsurprising that the literature formulating dominant imagined futures for climate and nuclear threats does not make many connections either. Recent literature on modern nuclear strategy still does not address climate change as a factor affecting nuclear politics (Freedman & Michaels, 2019; Narang & Sagan, 2023). The imagined futures of this dominant branch revolve around factors other than ongoing environmental transformations, notably multipolarity, new technologies, the proliferation of weapons to new states, and changes in the normative regimes governing nuclear

⁹ Available at: <https://www.scopus.com/>

¹⁰ The keywords used were: “nuclear weapon”, “nuclear bomb”, “nuclear arm”, “atom bomb”, “atomic bomb”, “nuclear disarmament”, “nuclear proliferation”, “nuclear posture”, “nuclear strategy”, “nuclear war”, “nuclear test”, “nuclear testing”, “nuclear deterrence”, “nuclear threat”, “nuclear non-proliferation”, “nuclear age”, “atomic age”, “nuclear diplomacy”, and “nuclear harm”.

¹¹ The keywords used were: “climate change”, “environmental change”, “climate crisis”, “climate vulnerability”, “climate resilience”, “climate threat”, “environmental threat”, “climate security”, “climate disaster”, “climate politics”, “climate policy”, “environmental policy”, “global warming”, “biodiversity”, “extreme weather”, “sea level”, “biosphere”, “earth system”, “tipping point”, “planetary boundary”, “ocean acidification”, “ozone depletion”, “flood”, “storm”, “drought”, “wildfire”, “extreme precipitation”, and any appearance of “climate” within three words of “adaptation” or “mitigation”.

¹² The full list is available at <https://www.sciencespo.fr/nuclear-knowledges/fr/actualites/supplement-to-existential-silos/>

¹³ It is not growing relative to the total number of results referencing either field. Publications on Scopus in general have grown exponentially, and increasingly rapidly since 2004 (Thelwall & Sud, 2022).

¹⁴ Roughly defined as literature in the “Social Sciences” subject area with nuclear-related terms in their titles or keywords.

Fig. 1. Publications per year, by type of relationship identified.

weapons decisions (Futter & Zala, 2021).

On the flip side, the environmental security field remains detached from nuclear weapons. Imagined futures of environmental security consist both of climate forecasting and of envisioned effects on security. The former are methodologically restricted from considering military impacts, given their unpredictability and exemption from emissions reporting (Rajaeifar et al., 2022). The latter, the relationship between climate futures and security, is contested, but no account includes nuclear weapons. Many focus on the security of human beings and communities from famine, natural disasters, and societal collapse (McDonald, 2021, pp. 81–90). Accounts which do operate at the level of state security often identify refugee flows, manageable threats to military preparedness, or political polarization as primary concerns (Welzer & Camiller, 2012, pp. 16–23). These are not threats nuclear weapons can address. A more intuitive intersection might concern the hypothesized proliferation of climate-driven conflicts, but these are assumed to be fought with conventional weapons only (Homer-Dixon, 2001; Welzer & Camiller, 2012). A partial explanation is that wars are mainly expected at a sub-state level in the Global South, especially in Africa, whereas nuclear weapons structure conflicts between states, predominantly the great powers (Sakaguchi et al., 2017, p. 639).

Yet even where this is not the case, climate-security connections fail to translate into nuclear thinking. Literature on India and Pakistan's nuclear deterrence relationship, for instance, does not consider the effects of environmental instability on conflict risk (Badri-Maharaj, 2019; Hagerty, 2019). This is in spite of research suggesting that climate change-driven water shortages could make nuclear war more likely (Mian, 2016).

We thus observe a gap, both in the quantitative scarcity of literature on interactions and in the seeming diversion in analytical foci between each body of work. Knowledge production on environmental change and the nuclear threat has proceeded as if the two threats will not meaningfully interact. That implicit assumption structuring scholarly inquiry is dangerous.

3. Imagining different futures: expanding existing connections

Existing literature does provide a set of well-established debates on three primary considerations: nuclear energy, governance solutions, and nuclear winter. These identify a locus for interaction but can better integrate the scale or the immediacy of the relevant problems.

3.1. Decarbonization, nuclear energy, and nuclear proliferation

The first of these relates to civilian nuclear energy and its links to nuclear weapons programs. Nuclear energy is seen by many as a potential – or even as the only – solution to limit greenhouse gas emissions, leading to talk of a climate-driven “nuclear renaissance”. This, however, clashes with concerns over nuclear weapons proliferation, as exemplified by the recent strikes on Iranian nuclear infrastructure (Mecklin, 2025). The expansion of nuclear energy is perceived as dangerous because it might spread dual-use technology, sensitive technical knowhow, and fissile materials (Miller & Sagan, 2009; Stulberg & Fuhrmann, 2013).¹⁵ Presented as a tradeoff of security from existential risks, nuclear energy can present a locus to prioritize climate change over nuclear weapons concerns (Dupont, 2008, p. 35) or vice versa (Socolow & Glaser, 2009, p. 35). Others treat it as a problem which managerial or technological improvements can avoid (Suzuki, 2010, for critics see Makhijani & Ramana, 2021).

Two limitations should be noted. First, this research often uncritically reproduces unsound assumptions about the inevitability of proliferation; most states have not pursued a nuclear arsenal even when they would have been technically capable of it (Pelopidas, 2015). Second, it worries about the possibility of *future* nuclear weapons in currently non-nuclear-armed states. This leaves open for study the ways current arsenals are intimately tied to civilian nuclear energy programs.

¹⁵ Inversely, nuclear disarmament could provide a source of fuel for the nuclear energy transition (World Nuclear Association, 2017).

Nuclear arsenals rely on a civilian nuclear energy sector to justify their costs, provide trained personnel, and produce weapons components. Militaries with nuclear weapons (or naval nuclear propulsion programs) therefore have an interest in maintaining a civilian sector and pose an obstacle to phaseouts of nuclear power (Stirling & Johnstone, 2018). Nuclear arsenals then encourage the uptake of nuclear energy. This is not unequivocally positive, since nuclear power may not always be the best climate solution. While it is certainly low-carbon, nuclear power plants are slow to build, expensive, and may not be as efficient as renewables, especially over the short term (Muellner et al., 2021; Ramana, 2024). Nuclear waste and the possibility of severe accidents remain major environmental concerns from which solar and wind power do not suffer (Schneider & Froggatt, 2023). Risks will also grow as environmental change progresses (Jordaan et al., 2019). Moreover, the demands of the military nuclear sector shaping the civilian sector may reduce its effectiveness as an energy provider. The choice of investing in nuclear energy over alternatives can then have potentially *negative* environmental consequences.

While the current literature expects nuclear energy only to create nuclear proliferation-related dangers, exploration of the nuclear industry in nuclear-armed expectation may identify ways that military goals could also create environmental risks.

3.2. Governance solutions for similar global threats

As noted above, much of the literature identifies ways in which nuclear weapons and environmental change are similar. Both are each viewed as problems which can only be solved through some level of global policy coordination because they, by nature, transcend national borders to threaten all of humanity. They were constitutive parts of the imagination of a ‘global’ realm, with the environmental effects of global nuclear fallout being foundational to later environmental movements (Masco, 2016).¹⁶ But they are similar in other ways, too. Notably, both are conceptualized as “collective action problems” and marked by difficulties in balancing (perceived) short-term benefits with less certain future risks. These underlying similarities suggest both would benefit from similar solutions.

For instance, changing societal risk evaluations would likely affect the valuing of both climate action and disarmament. Indeed, at the micro-level, exposure to a nuclear missile scare in Hawaii increased individuals’ participation in environmental activism (Bergstrand & Robertson, 2022). Anti-nuclear activism has historically translated into concern for the environment, with a particular relevance in Pacific island communities who have faced existential threats from both nuclear testing and sea level rise (Vaha, 2023; Williamson, 2020).

At the global level, prospects for addressing both issues improve with prospects for international cooperation. Most extremely, the transcendence of national sovereignty by supra-national state has been posited as the only complete solution for both climate change (Wainwright & Mann, 2018) and nuclear weapons governance (Craig, 2019; Deudney, 2008, Chapter 9). Even without this radical transformation, the experience of cooperation in one domain can contribute to mutual trust in international collaboration. Thus, even as it is proposed water shortages could drive conflict between India and Pakistan, other research suggests that the experience of cooperation on natural resource management might reduce tensions between the two countries (Homan & Burak, 2024). Inversely, nuclear disarmament could help progress cooperation on environmental change (Doyle, 2013, pp. 8–9). How best to conceptualize this positive feedback loop remains up for debate. The significance of progress on one issue for the other is likely contingent on specific political circumstances. Moreover, linking the two issues risks creating negative feedback loops, jeopardizing progress in one process when the other stalls. To think through future prospects, it is therefore relevant to study precisely how issue linkage between the two works in activism and governance for different cases and regions.

3.3. The climate impacts of nuclear war

Finally, a particular type of connection comes from work on “nuclear winter.” This research clearly assumes that nuclear weapons and the climate are interrelated, as a nuclear war would have catastrophic consequences for the biosphere. Even a ‘limited’ nuclear exchange involving 100 tactical nuclear weapons aimed at cities would result in a temperature drop of 0.7°C; 10 % less rain would fall (Robock et al., 2007; Toon et al., 2007). Climate disruptions would cause mass starvation (Xia et al., 2022, p. 587). All these effects are multiplied in larger nuclear exchanges, which could leave as many as 5 billion people starving and cause the extinction of a third of marine life and almost half of terrestrial quadrupeds (Kaiho, 2023, pp. 5–6).

While these effects clearly sit at the intersection of climate and nuclear, existing research does not clearly connect them interactively. The findings have significant implications for deterrence, since even unanswered nuclear strikes can have devastating consequences for the attacking state (Baum, 2015; Robock & Toon, 2012). Yet they have been shrugged off by nuclear security studies, which has not adapted its strategic thinking to include additional benefits of arsenal reductions or the reduced credibility of nuclear threats (Freedman & Michaels, 2019, p. 509). This reflects a limitation of the field’s assumptions about what is relevant to nuclear strategy.

When it comes to thinking on environmental change, studies on nuclear winter generally separate their object of study from the *ongoing* process of environmental change. Though a climatic event, nuclear winter is distinct from these processes in so far as it is a possible future phenomenon whose cause (nuclear war) is different from those behind current environmental transformations. Thus, models assume a baseline global climatic stability to better isolate the effects of nuclear war. Expectations about human impacts on the climate are mostly based on models accounting for different paths in terms of greenhouse gas emissions. These models do not always

¹⁶ This link is also true in a different sense, as the science of monitoring global nuclear testing laid the foundations for modern climate science, see: (Edwards, 2012).

include nuclear winter in their definition of possible futures. The authoritative IPCC reports, for instance, have never mentioned nuclear weapons except in relation to nuclear energy. Climate futures are most commonly based on scientific models of linear, predictable developments. That approach misses complex, non-linear ‘risk cascades’ stemming from overlapping threats or sudden tipping points (Kemp et al., 2022, p. 3; National Academy of Science, 2025, p. 110). This is not universal; some reports on climate change have accounted for other collapse scenarios (Randers, 2012, p. 240; Stern, 2006, p. 47). An awareness of alternative pathways to collapse is important, since no account of climate futures is complete without the inclusion of the continued possibility of nuclear winter, which itself could be worsened by a loss of biosphere integrity (Jehn, 2023).

4. Imagining different futures: an agenda to understand missed interactions

To undo the separation of nuclear weapons and environmental change, we set out from the premise that nuclear weapons and climate change are likely to be interactive to a significant degree. That implies a grounding of each in the research paradigms that have defined the other – treating nuclear weapons as existing in the physical environments of environmental research while conceptualizing climate policy as part of the same security environment as nuclear strategy. Doing so opens up a variety of material and strategic-political interactions to be studied and integrated into thinking on the future. Nuclear and environmental policy choices must be thought of as dynamically interconnected in ways that can create vicious circles, virtuous circles or trade-offs.

4.1. Material connections

The first set of interactions to map out consists of direct, material impacts. First, operating and maintaining a nuclear arsenal has detrimental effects on the environment even without nuclear use. Producing nuclear materials and delivery vehicles is highly energy intensive.¹⁷ The precise impacts of modern arsenals are not publicly reported. However, much nuclear weapons spending has historically been dedicated to the design, production, and maintenance of delivery vehicles.¹⁸ The impacts of such activities are likely comparable to the conventional arms sector, which is a disproportionately major producer of greenhouse gases. Neta Crawford estimates the US military industry produced around 51 million metric tons of CO₂ in 2019, significantly above average manufacturing emissions (Crawford, 2022, p. 196).¹⁹ An analysis of the UK sector suggests that including not only direct emissions from production, but total lifecycle emissions, significantly increases these estimates – from 6.5 to 11 million tons in 2017–18 (Parkinson, 2020, p. 2). The contribution of nuclear weapons manufacturing is unknown, though likely small: Nuclear forces account for some 10 % of defense acquisition spending in the US (Congressional Budget Office, 2025). The globalized nature of defense industries makes it difficult to estimate how this figure relates to estimated industrial emissions.

Further complicating the picture is the relationship between nuclear and conventional military emissions. Nuclear weapons might limit overall military climate impacts by reducing required amounts of conventional weaponry or by avoiding war. This touches upon the contentious question of nuclear weapons’ effect on peace, which we shall not resolve here. It is nonetheless worth noting that no consensus exists on the statistical correlation between nuclear possession and participation in armed conflicts (Bailo & Goldsmith, 2021; Bell & Miller, 2015). Nuclear weapons may even enable aggression in some cases (Bell, 2021). Nuclear weapons acquisition also does not seem to reduce investment in conventional arms beyond the short term, as states seek to fill gaps in deterrence credibility (Butt, 2015). In the most recent example of this, NATO is currently undertaking a rearmament program slated to increase carbon emissions by 200 million tons a year despite including three nuclear-armed states (Gayle, 2025).

Nuclear arsenals have environmental implications beyond delivery vehicle production. Producing, storing, maintaining, and dismantling military nuclear materials represents another significant element. Beyond their noted energy-intensity, these activities come with additional environmental impacts in the form of hazardous nuclear waste and the accidental or foreseen spread of radionuclides into the natural environment. The costs of waste management and cleanups are not typically considered in nuclear weapons politics. However, some estimation is needed, since continuing to rely on modernized nuclear arsenals will also require producing increasing amounts of environmental risk. Impacts are difficult to assess, not least because of secrecy and official denial (Sleiman, 2010). Past experience shows that radioactive contamination from nuclear production threatens biodiversity while undermining ecosystem resilience (Perry, 2021, pp. 55–72). Managing contamination will also become more challenging. Containment in areas previously affected by nuclear testing and production is becoming increasingly difficult as the environment changes. Contaminated icecaps in Greenland are melting (Colgan, 2018, pp. 39–43), waste containment in the Marshall Islands is leaking into the Pacific Ocean (Bordner et al., 2020), and swaths of contaminated organic material risk being spread on the winds of wildfires (Eriksen, 2022). Comprehensively mapping ecosystemic risks from nuclear weapons production across nuclear weapons sites, particularly those linked to weapons programs outside the US, and connecting these to future environmental change, presents another

¹⁷ An estimate places the share of commercial energy consumption devoted to producing nuclear arsenals as high as 5 % in the US and Soviet Union between 1950 and 1990 (Smil, 2004). The exact basis for this number is however not entirely clear, pointing to the need for further research into this neglected dimension of nuclear programs.

¹⁸ Indeed, over half of US nuclear weapons spending between 1940 and 1996 was dedicated the delivery systems (Schwartz, 1998, p. xxii).

¹⁹ This estimate is based on self-reported defense-industrial statistics. Another estimate in the same book arrives at 26–63 million metric tons of CO₂ based on employment figures (p.188). Given the inexactitude of this number and its inability to account for capital intensity, the quoted estimate seems more appropriate overall. However, future work could combine this data with an analysis of nuclear-weapons-related employment by defense sector to estimate weapons’ footprint.

gap in existing research.

This is suggestive of another important interaction: the risk of environmental change directly exacerbating nuclear-weapons-related dangers. Environmental change impacts the physical safety of nuclear bases, production facilities, and research labs. Their security is paramount to the functioning and control of the weapons as well as the safety of the environment surrounding them. The increasing subjection of nuclear bases to drought, fire, flooding, or extreme temperatures thus places the world at risk.

Such threats are identified most thoroughly for the US. The operational readiness of its land-based and airborne nuclear arsenal face limitations due to flooding, heat, and extreme rainfall (Kwong, 2023, pp. 13–24). At submarine bases, increased flooding poses a risk for the accessibility of installations for maintenance as well as submarines' access to port, while various forms of extreme weather could incapacitate personnel (Kwong, 2023, pp. 8–13). Similar problems threaten submarine bases in North Korea (Dill et al., 2021) and the UK (Dorfman, 2021). A more thorough accounting of the problems faced by nuclear weapons installations, particularly for non-coastal installations in climate-vulnerable India, Pakistan, and China, is missing.²⁰ Some risks are known but not systematically studied. In February 2024, operations at the Pantex nuclear weapons plant were halted due to forest fires, which have also threatened Los Alamos laboratory (Dahl, 2024). Large-scale forest fires raged around Russian nuclear installations in Siberia in 2010 (The Telegraph, 2010). These events will probably become more frequent in future.

Moreover, existing literature has focused on the financial cost of maintaining reliability for current defense purposes. This does not account for the possibility of compounding ecological crises around nuclear installations. More responsible thinking would also forecast vulnerabilities for radically different climate futures, including societal or infrastructural collapse. These should be part of climate adaptation and of nuclear force planning.

4.2. Strategic and political connections

Nuclear weapons and environmental change also interact by jointly affecting the international security environment. Environmental change could produce new conflicts, both within and between states, which in turn intersect with nuclear risks. First, intra-state destabilization should be imagined as carrying dangers of nuclear weapons accidents and misuse. Fears already exist that elements in the Pakistani military may hijack nuclear weapons if domestic power struggles escalate in a destabilized natural environment (Mian, 2016). North Korea might encounter similar issues as it faces famine-inducing drought in rice-producing regions (Lee et al., 2017, p. 579). Natural disasters and nuclear war also both feature in apocalyptic Christian visions of Armageddon prevalent in the United States, suggesting that environmental catastrophe may lead religious groups to embrace nuclear war in order to trigger the Rapture (Cook, 2004).

Second, environmental change may drive inter-state conflict. Such conflicts will be shaped by nuclear weapons, which may increase low-level conflict between nuclear-armed states (Snyder, 1965, pp. 98–99), or facilitate aggression towards non-nuclear-armed ones (Bell, 2021). Hypotheses on climate-driven nuclear confrontation have so far only been developed for South-East Asia. India and Pakistan both depend on the Indus River system for irrigation and electricity. The river's flow is projected to reduce significantly, which, combined with its position in the contested Jammu and Kashmir region, can trigger escalating confrontation (Asokan & Helfand, 2022). Comparable conflict dynamics in other nuclearized regions could and should be imagined. The changing Arctic, for instance, is identified as a locus of competition between Russia, the US, and European powers (Kraska, 2011). The intersection of increasingly accessible sea routes, rare earth elements, and militarization – notably the expanding presence of Russia's Northern Fleet nuclear attack submarines – creates possibilities for escalation. The Trump administration's threats to Greenland raise the prospect of conflict with Europe, including nuclear-armed France (France 24, 2025).

Alternatively, climate mitigation could itself become a source of conflict. States may resort to climate engineering technologies to attempt to limit environmental change effects. These technologies involve major unpredictable interventions in climate conditions, the consequences of which would likely spill over beyond target areas; one state's intervention could rob its neighbor of rainfall or crops (Sovacool et al., 2023). Conflict over (perceived) climate interventions is then another nexus of escalation. Moreover, deployment of geoengineering technologies would significantly worsen the impact of nuclear wars, as climate effects are compounded by sudden exit shocks when manmade modifications to the climate collapse (Baum et al., 2013; Tang & Kemp, 2021). The possibility of climate mitigation causing nuclear war could be particularly important to integrate into imagined futures. As climate change worsens, the temptation to resort to "easy" technical fixes may be increasingly strong (Oomen, 2024). Remembering that geoengineering – even if it were safe and effective from a biospheric perspective – could still trigger global devastation is then an important factor in weighing its costs and benefits.

Beyond specific pathways to conflict, it is crucial to consider if environmental change could alter the foundational assumptions of our understanding of nuclear threats. Finally, environmental change has potentially far-reaching implications for the functioning and value of nuclear deterrence. The value of a nuclear arsenal in an environmentally changed world depends on the imagined future climate security. Preoccupation with possible inter-state resource competition may make nuclear deterrence seem like appropriate insurance against neighbors' encroachments. However, this requires a specific and perhaps paradoxical vision of future threats. Nuclear weapons are ill-suited to credibly deter anything but high-level threats to state survival and could thus only deter existential threats to states' most essential resources. This deterrent effect relies in turn on the perceived ability to inflict unacceptable damage on an adversary, far exceeding their expected gains. Yet catastrophic environmental change presents a possibly equally great threat of

²⁰ One report does note China faces particularly intense sea level stresses (Stoetman et al., 2023, p. 24).

destruction. Faced with two simultaneously imminent existential threats, the risk-aversion supposedly instilled by nuclear arsenals may no longer be the rational response (Waltz, 1981) and may instead incentivize a logic of "national martyrdom" (Bayard de Volo, 2025, pp.10–12). Severe environmental change could thus undermine the reasons to expect nuclear threats would have a deterrent effect. That effect requires the deterrer to convince the deterree that they will not suffer unacceptable damage if they do not cross a red line. A state exposed to inevitable large environmental damage would not be convinced of this. Take the scenario of water shortages in India and Pakistan. In the context of severe droughts and dwindling river flows, both countries may find themselves in desperate need of water. If both face a potentially existential threat of starvation, ecological collapse, or social disruption, upstream India could divert river flows because it sees no other alternative to save itself. Pakistan similarly may see no other option than taking the water back by any means. Whether one dies of drought or by retaliation hardly matters. In a world with two competing imminent existential threats, nuclear threats are then potentially less effective.

This scenario is extreme, of course. Nonetheless, given the centrality of unacceptable costs in deterrence, a reflection on the implications of climate crises would be fruitful in navigating nuclear futures. The prospect of an "existential threat" from climate change may be belied by the insulation of government elites from threats to the 'state' in an abstract sense (Kucherenko, 2023). With this in mind, it seems productive to examine the effects of social collapse or meteorological extremes on leadership rationality in nuclear crises.

If climate threats are imagined in a less militarized, state-oriented fashion, the relative value of nuclear weapons declines. After all, they are of no use in responding to natural disasters, migration, or social upheaval. This suggests an argument for disarmament and the reallocation of nuclear budgets to climate adaptation and mitigation (Burt, 2010). Nuclear weapons' cost totaled around \$82.9 billion in 2022 across nuclear weapons states, according to ICAN's estimate (International Campaign to Abolish Nuclear Weapons, 2023). The \$43.7 billion of this coming from the United States almost equals the \$44.9 billion the Biden administration set aside to address environmental change that year (Vahlsing, 2022).²¹ These funding choices will become more high stakes the worse environmental change gets, in particular as the securing of nuclear installations against climate events will itself require more money.

Evidently, environmental change and nuclear weapons can affect one another through a range of mechanisms. These mutual effects imply that policy aimed at improving one can affect the other, creating virtuous circles (e.g. mutually sustaining attempts at international cooperation), vicious circles (e.g. climate instability causing environmentally harmful nuclear use), and tradeoffs (e.g. climate mitigation leading to nuclear conflict). Planning around the dynamics of these interactions will require a better understanding of them, but the first step is integrating thinking on the two issues. When making nuclear weapons decisions, the question of compounding effects for environmental change should always be asked and vice versa.

5. Conclusion

This paper has identified a pattern of compartmentalization in thinking on environmental change and nuclear weapons. Imagined futures rarely articulate possible interconnections, and often cast each threat as affecting a different kind of security. The five main nuclear-armed states' policy documents reveal a separation of strategic thinking in general doctrine as well as in specific adaptation and modernization programs. This pattern is replicated in the academic literature. Nuclear weapons and environmental change rarely appear in the same work and are usually treated as analogous or parallel phenomena when they do. As a result of this compartmentalized thinking, knowledge production progresses on an implicit assumption that the threats will not interact. Yet direct and indirect interactions must be understood to make responsible assessments of the future. Doing so adequately will also require awareness of other sources of external change. Defining the climate-nuclear nexus is thus a necessary though insufficient step in a broader effort to think dynamically about existential threats.

Integrating the imagined futures of these two threats will require new and better scholarship building on the few existing examples making those interactions conceivable. Familiar connections through nuclear energy, global governance, and nuclear winter only partially break the compartmentalization and can be deepened by exploring new pathways for interaction. In addition, we need to produce data on lesser-known interactions. This should start with an estimation of current nuclear weapons' environmental impact, both through production and possible accidents. Environmental change-driven risks to nuclear sites should be mapped more globally, with an eye to estimating future costs and benefits of nuclear arsenals. Thinking on nuclear strategy needs to integrate the climate into its assessments and consider that the future will not look like the present. The functioning and value of nuclear deterrence in a climate-changed future should be assessed. At the same time, environmental policy thinking should integrate interrelations with other ends of the world in assessing mitigation and adaptation options or their failure.

Disciplinarily and politically, it is tempting to assume that addressing one's existential threat of choice is all it takes to survive. However, we must overcome our tendency to thinking of major threats as isolated from the broader future landscape. If not, we would only trap ourselves in existential silos, which may become our tombs.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Sterre van Buuren: Writing – original draft. **Thomas Fraise:** Writing – original draft. **Benoît Pelopidas:** Writing – original draft.

²¹ Benefits of divestment from nuclear arsenals depend on its effect on conventional defense spending, see the discussion of the climate impact of weapons production above.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.

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Appendix. - List of Studied Policy Documents

China

- China: Arms Control and Disarmament. November 1995. Available online at <http://www.china.org.cn/e-white/army/index.htm>
- China's Military Strategy. 26 May 2015. Available online at http://www.china.org.cn/china/2015-05/26/content_35661433.htm
- China's Endeavors for Arms Control, Disarmament and Non-Proliferation. September 2005. Available online at <http://www.china.org.cn/english/features/book/140320.htm>
- China's National Defense in 2000. October 2000. Available online at <http://www.china.org.cn/e-white/2000/index.htm>
- China's National Defense in 2002. 9 December 2002. Available online at <http://www.china.org.cn/e-white/20021209/index.htm>
- China's National Defense in 2004. 27 December 2004. Available online at <http://www.china.org.cn/e-white/20041227/index.htm>
- China's National Defense in 2006. December 2006. Available online at <http://www.china.org.cn/english/features/book/194421.htm>
- China's National Defense in 2008. 20 January 2008. Available online at http://www.china.org.cn/government/whitepaper/node_7060059.htm
- China's National Defense in 2010. 31 March 2010. Available online at http://www.china.org.cn/government/whitepaper/node_7114675.htm
- China's National Defense in the New Era, 24 July 2019. Available online at https://english.www.gov.cn/archive/whitepaper/201907/24/content_WS5d3941ddc6d08408f502283d.html
- China's National Defense. July 1998. Available online at <http://www.china.org.cn/e-white/5/index.htm>
- China's Policies and Actions for Addressing Climate Change. 21 November 2021. Available online at http://www.china.org.cn/government/whitepaper/node_7172407.htm
- China's Policies and Actions for Addressing Climate Change. 22 November 2011. Available online at http://www.china.org.cn/government/whitepaper/node_7142680.htm
- China's Policies and Actions for Addressing Climate Change. 29 October 2008. Available online at http://www.china.org.cn/government/whitepaper/node_7055612.htm
- China's Policies and Actions for Addressing Climate Change. 5 November 2013. Available online at http://www.china.org.cn/government/whitepaper/node_7193982.htm
- Diversified Employment of China's Armed Forces. 16 April 2013. Available online at http://www.china.org.cn/government/whitepaper/node_7181425.htm
- 国家适应气候变化战略 (National Strategy for Climate Change Adaptation). 18 November 2013. Available online at <https://www.gov.cn/gzdt/att/att/site1/20131209/001e3741a2cc140f6a8701.pdf>
- 国家适应气候变化战略 2035 (National Strategy for Climate Change Adaptation 2035). 10 May 2022. Available online at https://www.gov.cn/zhengce/zhengceku/2022-06/14/content_5695555.htm

France

- Actualisation Stratégique 2021. Available online at <https://www.defense.gouv.fr/sites/default/files/dgris/REVUE%20STRat%202021%2004%2002%202021%20FR.pdf>
- Revue Stratégique de Défense et de Sécurité Nationale 2017. Available online at https://medias.vie-publique.fr/data_storage_s3/rapport/pdf/174000744.pdf
- Livre blanc sur la défense et la sécurité nationale 2013. Available online at <https://www.vie-publique.fr/rapport/33131-livre-blanc-sur-la-defense-et-la-securite-nationale-2013>
- Défense et Sécurité nationale: le livre blanc. Available online at https://medias.vie-publique.fr/data_storage_s3/rapport/pdf/084000341.pdf
- Plan nationale d'adaptation au changement climatique, 20 July 2011. Available online at: https://www.ecologie.gouv.fr/sites/default/files/ONERC_PNACC_1_complet.pdf
- Plan nationale d'adaptation au changement climatique, 20 december 2018. Available online at: https://www.ecologie.gouv.fr/sites/default/files/2018.12.20_PNACC2.pdf
- Livre Blanc sur la défense 1994. Available online at https://medias.vie-publique.fr/data_storage_s3/rapport/pdf/944048700.pdf
- Stratégie nationale bas-carbone. Available online at: https://www.ecologie.gouv.fr/sites/default/files/2020-03-25_MTES_SNBC2

pdf

Stratégie nationale d'adaptation au changement climatique. Available online at: https://www.ecologie.gouv.fr/sites/default/files/ONERC_PNACC_1_complet.pdf

Stratégie Climat & Défense. Available online at https://www.defense.gouv.fr/sites/default/files/tronc_commun/26.04.2022%20Strat%C3%A9gie%20Climat%20et%20D%C3%A9fense.pdf

Loi no. 2023–703 du 1er août 2023 relative à la programmation militaire pour les années 2024 à 2030 et portant diverses dispositions intéressant la défense. Available online at https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/download/pdf?id=8-zHNA9qOMD7YH_auHwAmJzKY6oT0Ac8uyatwTORrks=

Loi no. 2018–607 du 13 juillet 2018 relative à la programmation militaire pour les années 2019 à 2025 et portant diverses dispositions intéressant la défense. Available online at https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/download/pdf?id=js5RHeR4JqgSfiKAl7nT4YstvrVw7vibSIX3L_C8eE=

Russia

Climate Doctrine of the Russian Federation, 26 October 2023. Available online at <http://static.kremlin.ru/media/events/files/ru/MPUDKa1ymUgyAAy2AsmVhO3UW0oOIs9.pdf>

Climate Doctrine of the Russian Federation, 17 December 2009. Available online at https://www.mid.ru/ru/foreign_policy/official_documents/1672298/

Military Doctrine of the Russian Federation, 21 April 2000. Available online at [https://ru.wikisource.org/wiki/Военная_доктрина_Российской_Федерации_\(2000\)](https://ru.wikisource.org/wiki/Военная_доктрина_Российской_Федерации_(2000))

Military Doctrine of the Russian Federation, 25 December 2014. Available online at <http://www.scrf.gov.ru/security/military/document129/>

Military Doctrine of the Russian Federation, 5 February 2010. Available online at <http://www.kremlin.ru/supplement/461>

National Security Concept of the Russian Federation, 10 January 2000. Available online at <https://www.armscontrol.ru/start/rus/docs/sncon00.htm>

National Security Concept of the Russian Federation, 17 December 1997. Available online at <https://www.armscontrol.ru/start/rus/docs/snconold.htm>

National Security Strategy of the Russian Federation to 2020, 10 May 2009. Available online at <https://web.archive.org/web/20150403150504/http://www.scrf.gov.ru/documents/99.html>

National Security Strategy of the Russian Federation, 2 July 2021. Available online at <http://www.scrf.gov.ru/media/files/file/14wGRPqJvETSkUTYmhepzRochblj1jqh.pdf>

National Security Strategy of the Russian Federation, 31 December 2015. Available online at <http://publication.pravo.gov.ru/Document/View/0001201512310038>

Концепция общественной безопасности в Российской Федерации (Concept of Societal Security in the Russian Federation, 20 November 2013. Available online at <http://kremlin.ru/acts/news/19653>

Национальный план Мероприятий первого этапа адаптации к изменению климата (National action plan for the first stage of adaptation to climate change), 25 December 2019. Available online at <http://static.kremlin.ru/media/events/files/ru/ALzCFp4EbLAKAEuDwZpAxQ1W0Qel3mGT.pdf>

Основы государственной политики в области обеспечения ядерной и радиационной безопасности Российской Федерации на период до 2025 года (Foundations of Government Policy Relating to Ensuring the Nuclear and Radiological Security of the Russian Federation until 2025), 1 March 2012. Available online at <http://www.scrf.gov.ru/security/military/document128/>

Основы государственной политики в области обеспечения ядерной и радиационной безопасности Российской Федерации на период до 2025 года и дальнейшую перспективу (Foundations of Government Policy Relating to Ensuring the Nuclear and Radiological Security of the Russian Federation until 2025 and beyond), 13 October 2018. Available online at <http://pravo.gov.ru/proxy/ips/?docbody=&firstDoc=1&lastDoc=1&nd=102483840>

Основы государственной политики Российской Федерации в области ядерного сдерживания (Foundations of State Policy of the Russian Federation in the Area of Nuclear Deterrence), 2 June 2020. Available online at <http://www.kremlin.ru/acts/bank/45562>

Стратегия экономической безопасности Российской Федерации на период до 2030 года (Economic Security Strategy of the Russian Federation for the Period until 2030), 13 May 2015. Available online at <http://kremlin.ru/acts/bank/41921>

United Kingdom

A Strong Britain in an Age of Uncertainty: The National Security Strategy. Available online at <https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5a74cb2de5274a3cb286738d/national-security-strategy.pdf>

Defence Command Paper: Defence in a competitive age, March 2021. Available online at https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/6063061e8fa8f55b6ad297d0/CP411_-_Defence_Command_Plan.pdf

Defence Command Paper: Defence's response to a more contested and volatile world, July 2023. Available online at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/defence-command-paper-2023-defences-response-to-a-more-contested-and-volatile-world>

Global Britain in a competitive age: The Integrated Review of Security, Defence, Development and Foreign Policy. Available online at <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/global-britain-in-a-competitive-age-the-integrated-review-of-security-defence-development-and-foreign-policy>

Integrated Review Refresh 2023: Responding to a more contested and volatile world. Available online at <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/integrated-review-refresh-2023-responding-to-a-more-contested-and-volatile-world>

Ministry of Defence Climate Change and Sustainability Strategic Approach. Available online at https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/605ddbbe8fa8f5047d3a851e/20210326_Climate_Change_Sust_Strategy_v1.pdf

National Security Strategy and Strategic Defence and Security Review 2015. Available online at <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/national-security-strategy-and-strategic-defence-and-security-review-2015>

Net Zero Strategy: Build Back Greener. Available online at <https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/6194dfa4d3bf7f0555071b1b/net-zero-strategy-beis.pdf>

Nuclear Liabilities Management Strategy, May 2022. Available online at https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/628e3534d3bf7f1f433ae20d/Nuclear_Liabilities_Management_Strategy.pdf

Strategy for Defence Infrastructure. Available online at <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/strategy-for-defence-infrastructure>

The National Adaptation Programme and the Third Strategy for Climate Adaptation Reporting: Making the country resilient to a changing climate, July 2018. Available online at <https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/64b6789361adff001301b22e/national-adaptation-programme-2018.pdf>

The National Adaptation Programme: Making the country resilient to a changing climate, July 2013. Available online at <https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5b507f15e5274a73271ac8be/pb13942-nap-20130701.pdf>

The National Security Strategy of the United Kingdom Security in an interdependent world. Available online at: <https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5a7c68abed915d696ccfc92a/7291.pdf>

The National Security Strategy of the United Kingdom: Update 2009: Security for the Next Generation. Available online at https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/229001/7590.pdf

The Third National Adaptation Programme (NAP3) and the Fourth Strategy for Climate Adaptation Reporting. Available online at: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/64ba74102059dc00125d27a7/The_Third_National_Adaptation_Programme.pdf

United States of America

2022 National Defense Strategy of the United States of America. Available online at <https://www.defense.gov/Portals/1/Documents/pubs/2022-Defense-Strategic-Guidance-Summary.pdf>

2022 Nuclear Posture Review. Available online at <https://www.defense.gov/Portals/1/Documents/pubs/2022-Nuclear-Posture-Review-Report.pdf>

Climate Action 2030, Department of the Navy. Available online at <https://www.navy.mil/Portals/1/Documents/Department%20of%20the%20Navy%20Climate%20Action%202030%20220531.pdf>

Department of Defense Climate Adaptation Plan, September 1, 2021. Available online at: <https://www.sustainability.gov/pdfs/dod-2021-cap.pdf>

Department of Defense Climate Risk Analysis, October 2021. Available online at <https://media.defense.gov/2021/Oct/21/2002877353/-1/-1/0/DOD-CLIMATE-RISK-ANALYSIS-FINAL.PDF>

Department of the Air Force Climate Action Plan, October 2022. Available online at https://www.safie.hq.af.mil/Portals/78/documents/Climate/DAF%20Climate%20Action%20Plan.pdf?ver=YcQAZsGM_Xom3DkNP_fL3g%3d%3d

Executive Order on Tackling the Climate Crisis at Home and Abroad, January 27, 2021. Available at: <https://www.whitehouse.gov/briefing-room/presidential-actions/2021/01/27/executive-order-on-tackling-the-climate-crisis-at-home-and-abroad/>

Interim National Security Strategic Guidance, March 2021. Available online at <https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/NSC-1v2.pdf>

The Long-Term Strategy of the United States: Pathways to Net-Zero Greenhouse Gas Emissions by 2050, November 2021. Available online at: <https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/us-long-term-strategy.pdf>

National Defense Strategy, June 2008. Available online at <https://archive.defense.gov/pubs/2008nationaldefensestrategy.pdf>

National Security Strategy of the United States of America, December 2017. Available online at <https://trumpwhitehouse.archives.gov/wp-content/uploads/2017/12/NSS-Final-12-18-2017-0905.pdf>

National Security Strategy, February 2015. Available online at https://obamawhitehouse.archives.gov/sites/default/files/docs/2015_national_security_strategy.pdf

National Security Strategy, May 2010. Available online at https://obamawhitehouse.archives.gov/sites/default/files/rss_viewer/national_security_strategy.pdf

National Security Strategy, October 2022. Available online at <https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2022/10/National-Security-Strategy-2022.pdf>

Nuclear Posture Review 2018. Available online at <https://media.defense.gov/2018/Feb/02/2001872886/-1/-1/1/2018-NUCLEAR-POSTURE-REVIEW-FINAL-REPORT.PDF>

Nuclear Posture Review Report 2010. Available online at https://www.defense.gov/Portals/1/Archive/Report_Web_NPR%202010.pdf

Quadrennial Defense Review 2014. Available online at https://archive.defense.gov/pubs/2014_Quadrennial_Defense_Review.pdf

Quadrennial Defense Review Report, February 6, 2006. Available online at <https://archive.defense.gov/qdr/report/Report20060203.pdf>

Quadrennial Defense Review Report, February, 2010. Available online at <https://archive.defense.gov/qdr/QDR%20as%20of%20>

2026JAN10%201600.pdf

Quadrennial Defense Review Report, September 30, 2001. Available online at <https://archive.defense.gov/pubs/qdr2001.pdf>

Report of the Quadrennial Defense Review, May 1997. Available online at https://archive.defense.gov/pubs/qdr/QDR_Report.pdf

Summary of the 2018 National Defense Strategy of the United States of America. Available online at <https://dod.defense.gov/Portals/1/Documents/pubs/2018-National-Defense-Strategy-Summary.pdf>

The National Defense Strategy of the United States of America, March 2005. Available online at <https://archive.defense.gov/news/Mar2005/d20050318nds1.pdf>

The National Security Strategy of the United States of America, March 2006. Available online at <https://georgewbush-whitehouse.archives.gov/nsc/nss/2006/>

The National Security Strategy of the United States of America, September 2002. Available online at <https://georgewbush-whitehouse.archives.gov/nsc/nss/2002/>

U.S. Army Corps of Engineers Climate Action Plan. Available online at 20 June 2024. <https://www.sustainability.gov/pdfs/usace-2021-cap.pdf>

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- Armed Forces: Nuclear Deterrent: Hearing on Volume 668, House of Lords (2007). (<https://hansard.parliament.uk/Lords/2007-01-24/debates/07012469000007/ArmedForcesNuclearDeterrent>).
- Asokan, A., & Helfand, I. (2022). Climate change and water scarcity will increase risk of nuclear catastrophe in South Asia. *Bulletin of the Atomic Scientists*, 78(4), 214–217. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00963402.2022.2087382>
- Badri-Maharaj, S. (2019). *Indian nuclear strategy: Confronting the potential threat from both China and Pakistan*. Taylor & Francis Group.
- Bailo, F., & Goldsmith, B. E. (2021). No paradox here? Improving theory and testing of the nuclear stability–instability paradox with synthetic counterfactuals. *Journal of Peace Research*, 58(6), 1178–1193. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00223433211018501>
- Baum, S. D., et al. (2013). Double catastrophe: Intermittent stratospheric geoengineering induced by societal collapse. *Environment Systems Decisions*, 33(1), 168–180. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10669-012-9429-y>
- Baum, S. D. (2015). Winter-safe deterrence: The risk of nuclear winter and its challenge to deterrence. *Contemporary Security Policy*, 36(1), 123–148. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13523260.2015.1012346>
- Bayard de Volo, L. (2025). Cuba's Missile Crisis and the Logic of National Martyrdom. *Security Studies*, 34(2), 292–319. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09636412.2025.2489351>
- Beckert, J. (2016). *Imagined futures: Fictional expectations and capitalist dynamics*. Harvard university press.
- Bell, M.S. (2021). Nuclear Reactions: How Nuclear-Armed States Behave. Cornell University Press. <https://doi.org/10.7298/13z2-td29>
- Bell, M. S., & Miller, N. L. (2015). Questioning the effect of nuclear weapons on conflict. *Journal of Conflict Resolution*, 59(1), 74–92. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022002713499718>
- Bergstrand, K., & Robertson, C. (2022). Threat and emotions: Mobilizing and attitudinal outcomes of a ballistic missile scare. *Social Problems*, 69(1), 184–202. <https://doi.org/10.1093/socpro/spaa048>
- Bordner, A. S., et al. (2020). Colonial dynamics limit climate adaptation in Oceania: Perspectives from the Marshall Islands. *Global Environmental Change*, 61, Article 102054. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2020.102054>
- Burt, P. (2010). A replacement for Trident – can the UK afford it? *International Journal of Green Economics*. (<https://www.inderscienceonline.com/doi/10.1504/IJGE.2009.031333>).
- Butt, A. I. (2015). Do nuclear weapons affect the guns-butter trade-off? Evidence on nuclear substitution from Pakistan and beyond. *Conflict, Security Development*, 15(3), 229–257. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14678802.2015.1055120>
- Cabinet Office. (2008). The National Security Strategy of the United Kingdom [Cm 7291].
- Climate Action Tracker. (2024). Climate Action Tracker. (<https://climateactiontracker.org/>).
- Colgan, J. D. (2018). Climate change and the politics of military bases. *Global Environmental Politics*, 18(1), 33–51. https://doi.org/10.1162/GLEP_a_00443
- Congressional Budget Office. (2025). Projected Costs of U.S. Nuclear Forces, 2025 to 2034. (<https://www.cbo.gov/publication/61362>).
- Cook, M. L. (2004). Christian apocalypticism and weapons of mass destruction. In In. S. H. Hashmi, & S. P. Lee (Eds.), *Ethics and weapons of mass destruction: religious and secular perspectives* (pp. 200–212). Cambridge University Press.
- Cour des comptes. (2024). Le rapport public annuel 2024. L'action publique en faveur de l'adaptation au changement climatique, Vol.1. (<https://www.ccomptes.fr/fr/publications/le-rapport-public-annuel-2024>).
- Craig, C. (2019). Solving the nuclear dilemma: Is a world state necessary? *Journal of International Political Theory*, 15(3), 349–366.
- Crawford, N. (2022). The Pentagon, climate change, and war: Charting the rise and fall of U.S. military emissions. The MIT Press.
- Dahl, K. (2024, March 7). Wildfire Threat to Texas Nuclear Weapons Facility Highlights Intersecting Risks. The Equation - Union of Concerned Scientists. (<https://blog.ucs.org/kristy-dahl/wildfire-threat-to-texas-nuclear-weapons-facility-highlights-intersecting-risks/>).
- Defence Infrastructure Organisation. (2017). Climate Impact Risk Assessment: Annex A - Estate and Climatic Information HM Naval Base Clyde. (https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/878527/20200116-FOI13198.pdf).
- Deudney, D.H. (2008). *Bounding Power: Republican Security Theory from the Polis to the Global Village*. Princeton University Press.
- Dill, C., et al. (2021). Converging crises in North Korea: Security, stability & climate change. Woodwell Climate Research Center. *Converging Risks Lab, and Council on Strategic Risks*.
- Dorfman, P. (2021). Climate Impact UK Nuclear Military. Nuclear Consulting Group. (<https://www.nuclearconsult.org/wp/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/Climate-Change-UK-Nuclear-Military-Sept21.pdf>).
- Doyle, J.E. (2013). Why Eliminate Nuclear Weapons? Survival. (<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00396338.2013.767402>).
- Dupont, A. (2008). The strategic implications of climate change. *Survival*, 50(3), 29–54. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00396330802173107>
- Edwards, P. N. (2012). Entangled histories: Climate science and nuclear weapons research. *Bulletin of the Atomic Scientists*, 68(4), 28–40. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0096340212451574>
- Egeland, K. (2025). Disentangling the Nexus of Nuclear Weapons and Climate Change—A Research Agenda. *International Studies Review*, 27(1). <https://doi.org/10.1093/isr/viaf003>

- Eriksen, C. (2022). Wildfires in the atomic age: Mitigating the risk of radioactive smoke. Article 1. *Fire*, 5(1). <https://doi.org/10.3390/fire5010002>
- European Commission. (2024). GHG emissions of all world countries. Publications Office. (<https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/4002897>).
- France 24. (2025, January 8). France warns Trump against threatening EU 'sovereign borders' after Greenland comments. (<https://www.france24.com/en/europe/20250108-france-warns-trump-against-threatening-eu-sovereign-borders-after-greenland-comments>).
- Fratantuono, M. et al. (2022). Climate Vulnerability Assessment and Resilience Plan (No. LNLN-TR-840422, 1890099, 1061870). Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory. <https://doi.org/10.2172/1890099>.
- Freedman, L., & Michaels, J. (2019). *The Evolution of Nuclear Strategy: New, Updated, and Completely Revised* (4th ed.). Palgrave Macmillan.
- Futter, A., & Zala, B. (2021). Strategic non-nuclear weapons and the onset of a Third Nuclear Age. *European Journal of International Security*, 6(3), 257–277. <https://doi.org/10.1017/eis.2021.2>
- Gayle, D. (2025, May 29). Revealed: Nato rearmament could increase emissions by 200m tonnes a year. *The Guardian*. (<https://www.theguardian.com/environment/2025/may/29/nato-military-spending-could-increase-emissions-study-finds>).
- Green, F. (2022). Fossil free zones: A proposal. *Climate Policy*, 22(9–10), 1356–1362. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2022.2118657>
- Hagerty, D.T. (2019). *Nuclear Weapons and Deterrence Stability in South Asia*. Springer International Publishing AG.
- Homan, P., & Burak, T. (2024). India, Pakistan, and environmental security: A path to peace. In In. T. T. Gibson, & K. W. Jefferson (Eds.), *International Security Studies and Technology* (pp. 47–65). Edward Elgar Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781035336241.00009>.
- Homer-Dixon, T.F. (2001). *Environment, Scarcity, and Violence*. Princeton University Press.
- House of Commons Defence Committee. (2006a). The Future of the UK's Strategic Nuclear Deterrent: The Manufacturing and Skills Base (No. HC 59). (<https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/cm200607/cmselect/cmdfence/59/59.pdf>).
- House of Commons Defence Committee. (2006b). The Future of the UK's Strategic Nuclear Deterrent: The Strategic Context (No. HC986). (<https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/cm200506/cmselect/cmdfence/986/986.pdf>).
- House of Commons Defence Committee. (2007). The Future of the UK's Strategic Nuclear Deterrent: The White Paper (No. HC 225-II). (<https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/cm200607/cmselect/cmdfence/225/225ii.pdf>).
- International Campaign to Abolish Nuclear Weapons. (2023). Wasted: 2022 Global Nuclear Weapons Spending. ICAN. (https://www.icanw.org/wasted_2022_global_nuclear_weapons_spending).
- Jehn, F. U. (2023). Anthropocene under dark skies: The compounding effects of nuclear winter and overstepped planetary boundaries. In In. D. Zimmer, T. A. Undheim, & P. N. Edwards (Eds.), *Intersections, Reinforcements, Cascades: Proceedings of the 2023 Stanford Existential Risks Conference* (pp. 119–132). Stanford University.
- Jordaan, S. M., et al. (2019). The climate vulnerabilities of global nuclear power. *Global Environmental Politics*, 19(4), 3–13. https://doi.org/10.1162/glep_a_00527
- Kaiho, K. (2023). An animal crisis caused by pollution, deforestation, and warming in the late 21st century and exacerbation by nuclear war. *Heliyon*, 9(4), Article e15221. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e15221>
- Kemp, L., et al. (2022). Climate endgame: Exploring catastrophic climate change scenarios. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 119(34), Article e2108146119. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2108146119>
- Kraska, J. (2011). *Arctic Security in an Age of Climate Change*. Cambridge University Press.
- Kristensen, H. et al. (2025, March 3). Status of World Nuclear Forces. Federation of American Scientists. (<https://fas.org/initiative/status-world-nuclear-forces/>).
- Kucherenko, S. (2023). Existential threat as a Casus Belli. *Conatus*, 8(2), 299–312. <https://doi.org/10.12681/cjp.35080>
- Kwong, J. (2023). How Climate Change Challenges the U.S. Nuclear Deterrent. Carnegie Endowment for International Peace. (https://carnegieendowment.org/files/Kwong-Climate_Change_and_Nuclear_Weapons.pdf).
- Lee, S.-H., et al. (2017). Assessment of the impact of climate change on drought characteristics in the Hwanghae Plain, North Korea using time series SPI and SPEI: 1981–2100. *Water*, 9(8), 579. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w9080579>
- Lenton, T., et al. (2023). Quantifying the human cost of global warming. *Nature Sustainability*, 6(10), 1237–1247. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-023-01132-6>
- Makhijani, A., & Ramana, M. V. (2021). Can small modular reactors help mitigate climate change? *Bulletin of the Atomic Scientists*, 77(4), 207–214. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00963402.2021.1941600>
- Masco, J. (2016). Terraforming planet Earth: The age of fallout. In In. R. Van Munster, & C. Sylvest (Eds.), *The Politics of Globality since 1945: Assembling the Planet*. Routledge.
- Maurer, P. (2016). Armes nucléaires: Mettre fin à une menace pour l'humanité. *Revue Internationale de La Croix-Rouge*, 899.
- McDonald, M. (2021). *Ecological Security: Climate Change and the Construction of Security*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009024495>.
- McDonald, M. (2024). Fit for purpose? Climate change, security and IR. *International Relations*, 38(3), 313–330. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00471178241268270>
- Mecklin, J. (2025, June 12). Israel attacks Iran, targeting military leaders, nuclear facilities, and nuclear scientists. Bulletin of the Atomic Scientists. (<https://thebulletin.org/2025/06/israel-attacks-iran-targeting-military-leaders-nuclear-facilities-and-nuclear-scientists/#post-heading>).
- Mian, Z. (2016, December 7). Kashmir, climate change, and nuclear war. Bulletin of the Atomic Scientists. (<https://thebulletin.org/2016/12/kashmir-climate-change-and-nuclear-war/>).
- Miller, S. E., & Sagan, S. D. (2009). Nuclear power without nuclear proliferation? *Daedalus*, 138(4), 7–18. <https://doi.org/10.1162/daed.2009.138.4.7>
- Mills, C. (2023). Replacing the UK's strategic nuclear deterrent: Progress of the Dreadnought class (Research Briefing No. 8010). House of Commons Library. (<https://researchbriefings.files.parliament.uk/documents/CBP-8010/CBP-8010.pdf>).
- Montoya, N., & Kemp, R.S. (2023, March 17). Launch Under Attack: A Sword of Damocles. War on the Rocks. (<https://warontherocks.com/2023/03/launch-under-attack-a-sword-of-damocles/>).
- Muellner, N., et al. (2021). Nuclear energy—The solution to climate change? *Energy Policy*, 155, Article 112363. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2021.112363>
- Narang, V., & Sagan, S.D. (Eds.). (2023). *The Fragile Balance of Terror: Deterrence in the New Nuclear Age*. Cornell University Press.
- National Academy of Science. (2025). Potential environmental effects of nuclear war. Report from the Committee on Independent Study on Potential Environmental Effects of Nuclear War. National Academies Press.
- National Nuclear Security Administration. (2023). Fiscal Year 2023 Stockpile Stewardship and Management Plan – Biennial Plan Summary [Report to Congress]. US Department of Energy. (https://www.energy.gov/sites/default/files/2023-04/FY23%20SSMP_FINAL.pdf).
- Newell, P., et al. (2022). Building a fossil fuel non-proliferation treaty: Key elements. *Earth System Governance*, 14, Article 100159. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esg.2022.100159>
- Oomen, J. (2024). Producing the inevitability of solar radiation modification in climate politics. *Ethics International Affairs*, 38(3), 287–301. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0892679424000273>
- Palombella, G. (2023). Irreversible choices and future generations' rights. *Kutafin Law Review*, 10(1), 110–136. <https://doi.org/10.17803/2713-0533.2023.1.23.110-136>
- Parkinson, S. (2020). The Environmental Impacts of the UK Military Sector. Scientists for Global Responsibility and Declassified UK. (<https://www.sgr.org.uk/publications/environmental-impacts-uk-military-sector>).
- Parly, F. (2021, February 19). Déclaration sur les sous-marins nucléaires lanceur d'engins de 3ème génération. (<http://www.vie-publique.fr/discours/278679-florence-parly-19022021-sous-marins-nucleaires-lanceur-dengins>).
- Pelopidas, B. (2015). Renunciation: Restraint and rollback. In J. F. Pilat, & N. E. Busch (Eds.), *Routledge Handbook of Nuclear Proliferation and Policy* (pp. 337–348). Routledge.
- Pelopidas, B. (2016). Nuclear weapons scholarship as a case of self-censorship in security studies. *Journal of Global Security Studies*, 1(4), 326–336. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jogss/ogw017>
- Pelopidas, B. (2017). The unbearable lightness of luck: Three sources of overconfidence in the manageability of nuclear crises. *European Journal of International Security*, 2(2), 240–262. <https://doi.org/10.1017/eis.2017.6>

- Pelopidas, B. (2020). Power, luck, and scholarly responsibility at the end of the world(s). *International Theory*, 12(3), 459–470. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1752971920000299>
- Pelopidas, B., Taha, H., & Vaughan, T. (2024). How dawn turned into dusk: Scoping and closing possible nuclear futures after the Cold War. *Journal of Strategic Studies*, 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01402390.2023.2290441>
- Perry, J. (2021). Nuclear weapons and the environment: An ecological case for non-proliferation. Lexington Books.
- Pinson, A.O. et al. (2021). DoD Installation Exposure to Climate Change at Home and Abroad. U.S. Army Corps of Engineers.
- Proposition de loi constitutionnelle visant à protéger et à garantir la force de dissuasion nucléaire (No. No. 825). (2023). Assemblée Nationale. (https://www.assemblee-nationale.fr/dyn/16/textes/116b0825_proposition-loi.pdf).
- Rajaeifar, M. A., Belcher, O., Parkinson, S., Neimark, B., Weir, D., Ashworth, K., ... Heidrich, O. (2022). Decarbonize the military — mandate emissions reporting. *Nature*, 611(7934), 29–32. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-022-03444-7>
- Ramana, M.V. (2024). Nuclear is not the solution: The folly of atomic power in the age of climate change. Verso.
- Randers, J. (2012). 2052: A Global Forecast for the Next Forty Years. Chelsea Green.
- Rendall, M. (2007). Nuclear weapons and intergenerational exploitation. *Security Studies*, 16(4), 525–554. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09636410701741070>
- Richardson, K., et al. (2023). Earth beyond six of nine planetary boundaries. *Science Advances*, 9(37), Article eadh2458. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.adh2458>
- Robock, A., et al. (2007). Climatic consequences of regional nuclear conflicts. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 7, 2003–2012. (www.atmos-chem-phys.net/7/2003/2007/).
- Robock, A., & Toon, O. B. (2012). Self-assured destruction: The climate impacts of nuclear war. *Bulletin of the Atomic Scientists*, 68(5), 66–74. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0096340212459127>
- Rodgers, J., & Hersman, R. (2021, February). Nuclear Modernization under Competing Pressures. Center for Strategic & International Studies. (<https://www.csis.org/analysis/nuclear-modernization-under-competing-pressures>).
- Sakaguchi, K., et al. (2017). Climate wars? A systematic review of empirical analyses on the links between climate change and violent conflict. *International Studies Review*, 19(4), 622–645. <https://doi.org/10.1093/isr/vix022>
- Schlosser, E. (2013). Command and Control: Nuclear weapons, the Damascus Accident, and the illusion of safety. The Penguin Press.
- Schneider, M., & Froggatt, A. (2023). The World Nuclear Industry Status Report 2019. A Mycle Schneider Consulting Project. https://doi.org/10.1142/9789811213953_0021
- Schwartz, S.I. (1998). Atomic Audit: The Costs and Consequences of U.S. Nuclear Weapons Since 1940. Brookings Institutions Press.
- Sears, N. A. (2021). International politics in the age of existential threats. *Journal of Global Security Studies*, 6(3), Article ogaa027. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jogss/ogaa027>
- Sherwin, M.J. (2020). Gambling with Armageddon: Nuclear Roulette from Hiroshima to the Cuban Missile Crisis, 1945-1962. Alfred A. Knopf.
- Sleiman, M. (2010). Shutting down Dimona: Israel's nuclear programme, arsenal and environmental threat. *Contemporary Arab Affairs*, 3(4), 437–479. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17550912.2010.528203>
- Smil, V. (2004). War and energy. In C. J. Cleveland (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of Energy* (pp. 363–371). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B0-12-176480-X/00016-4>
- Snyder, G. H. (1965). The balance of power and the balance of terror. In In. P. Seabury (Ed.), *The Balance of Power* (pp. 184–201). Chandler.
- Socolow, R. H., & Glaser, A. (2009). Balancing risks: Nuclear energy & climate change. *Daedalus*, 138(4), 31–44. <https://doi.org/10.1162/daed.2009.138.4.31>
- Sovacool, B. K., Baum, C., & Low, S. (2023). The next climate war? Statecraft, security, and weaponization in the geopolitics of a low-carbon future. *Energy Strategy Reviews*, 45, Article 101031. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esr.2022.101031>
- Steffen, Richardson, W., et al. (2015). Planetary boundaries: Guiding human development on a changing planet. *Science*, 347(6223), Article 1259855. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1259855>
- Stern, N. (2006). The Economics of Climate Change (Supporting Document to Pre-Budget Report 2006 (CM 6984)). Stationery Office.
- Stirling, A., & Johnstone, P. (2018). A Global Picture of Industrial Interdependencies Between Civil and Military Nuclear Infrastructures (SSRN Scholarly Paper No. 3230021). <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3230021>
- Stoetman, A. et al. (2023). Military capabilities affected by climate change. Clingendael. (https://www.clingendael.org/sites/default/files/2023-01/Military_capabilities_affected_by_climate_change.pdf).
- Stulberg, A.N., & Fuhrmann, M. (2013). The Nuclear Renaissance and International Security. Stanford University Press.
- Suzuki, A. (2010). Toward a robust nuclear management system. *Daedalus*, 139(1), 82–92.
- Tang, A., & Kemp, L. (2021). A fate worse than warming? Stratospheric aerosol injection and global catastrophic risk. *Frontiers in Climate*, 3, Article 720312. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fclim.2021.720312>
- The Telegraph. (2010, August 10). Russia declares state of emergency in nuclear town as wildfires blaze. (<https://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/worldnews/europe/russia/7935828/Russia-declares-state-of-emergency-in-nuclear-town-as-wildfires-blaze.html>).
- Thelwall, M., & Sud, P. (2022). Scopus 1900–2020: Growth in articles, abstracts, countries, fields, and journals. *Quantitative Science Studies*, 3(1), 37–50. <https://doi.org/10.1162/qss.a.00177>
- Toon, O. B., et al. (2007). Atmospheric effects and societal consequences of regional scale nuclear conflicts and acts of individual nuclear terrorism. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 7(8). <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-7-1973-2007>
- U.S. Department of Defense. (2022, October 27). 2022 National Defense Strategy of the United States of America. (<https://archive.fo/6l04M>).
- Vaha, M. (2023). The Pacific's Nuclear Legacy in the Context of the Climate Crisis. Asia-Pacific Leadership Network. (<https://www.apln.network/projects/voices-from-pacific-island-countries/the-pacifics-nuclear-legacy-in-the-context-of-the-climate-crisis>).
- Vahlsing, C. (2022, April 4). Quantifying Risks to the Federal Budget from Climate Change. The White House. (<https://www.whitehouse.gov/omb/briefing-room/2022/04/04/quantifying-risks-to-the-federal-budget-from-climate-change/>).
- Vogler, A. (2023). Barking up the tree wrongly? How national security strategies frame climate and other environmental change as security issues. *Political Geography*, 105, Article 102893. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polgeo.2023.102893>
- Wainwright, J., & Mann, G. (2018). Climate Leviathan: A Political Theory of Our Planetary Future. Verso.
- Waltz, K. N. (1981). The spread of nuclear weapons: more may be better: Introduction, 1–1 *The Adelphi Papers*, 21(171). <https://doi.org/10.1080/05679328108457394>
- Welzer, H., & Camiller, P. (2012). Climate Wars: What People Will Be Killed for in the 21st Century. Polity Press.
- Williamson, J. (2020). Nuclear war, climate change, and medical activism. *The Lancet Planetary Health*, 4(6), e221–e222. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196\(20\)30127-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196(20)30127-3)
- World Nuclear Association. (2017). Military Warheads as a Source of Nuclear Fuel. (<https://world-nuclear.org/information-library/nuclear-fuel-cycle/uranium-resources/military-warheads-as-a-source-of-nuclear-fuel.aspx>).
- Xia, L., et al. (2022). Global food insecurity and famine from reduced crop, marine fishery and livestock production due to climate disruption from nuclear war soot injection. *Nature Food*, 3(8). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43016-022-00573-0>
- Zala, B. (2024). Should AI stay or should AI go? First strike incentives & deterrence stability. *Australian Journal of International Affairs*, 78(2), 154–163. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10357718.2024.2328805>